

UNIDIRECTIONAL CARBON FIBRE REINFORCED POLYVINYLIDENE FLUORIDE: IMPACT OF ATMOSPHERIC PLASMA FLUORINATION ON COMPOSITE PERFORMANCE

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ABSTRACT

Poly (vinylidene fluoride) (PVDF) exhibits excellent toughness and corrosion resistance to severe environmental stresses and offers great potential as a matrix for the development of ultra-inert fibre reinforced composites. For these reasons, unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced (PVDF) composites were manufactured using a powder impregnation process with integrated inline continuous atmospheric plasma fluorination (APF) of carbon fibres to produce unidirectional carbon fibre/PVDF tapes with a fibre volume fraction of 60 %. Carbon fibre/PVDF tapes were processed into composite laminate test pieces by compression moulding and interface dominated properties were studied. The short-beam shear test results show an improvement of up to 70% for the composite laminates containing atmospheric plasma fluorinated T700 carbon fibres with a fluorine content of 3.7at.-%, as determined by XPS. The flexural strength and modulus of the laminated carbon fibre/PVDF composites containing APF treated T700 carbon fibres also increased by 45 % and 38%, respectively.

Keywords: adhesion, atmospheric plasma fluorination, carbon fibre, continuous processing and manufacturing, mechanical testing

INTRODUCTION

The oil and gas industry continues to explore and develop deep-sea oilfields in which materials encounter extreme conditions in such operations that require superior material performance and durability. The materials have to withstand combined severe service conditions, aggressive media (sweet and sour well fluids), high abrasion, high but fluctuating temperatures, pressure differences and mechanical load. Conventional engineering materials, such as steel, which are heavy and require corrosion protection, used as risers, flowlines and choke and kill lines have reached their limits because of their poor chemical resistance and damage tolerance and/ or the high costs involved in supporting their own weight [1]. Therefore, they will have to be replaced by non-corroding and lighter alternative materials if deeper sea reservoirs are to be explored. Polymer composites might have the potential to overcome such limitations thus enabling new design strategies for cost effective, weight and energy saving materials [2,3]. Spoolable fibre reinforced thermoplastic pipes are not intrinsically novel as high performance carbon fibre reinforced polyetheretherketone (PEEK) composites have already been developed for use in transporting highly corrosive fluids including crude oil, brine and various gases at high service pressures [4,5]. This is because carbon fibre reinforced PEEK is well established and recognised because of its light weight,

possesses excellent mechanical properties and has superb resistance when exposed to extreme chemical and mechanical conditions [6,7]. However, PEEK is expensive compared to many other high performance polymers and difficult to process as it requires processing temperatures of around 400°C [8]. On the other hand, poly vinylidene fluoride (PVDF), like many other fluoropolymers, does not only exhibit excellent toughness but it has also the same heat deflection temperature (140°C) at 0.46 MPa as polyamide 12 (PA12). However, PVDF has a much lower water absorption (0.03 %) compared to PA 12 (1.4 %), which is the key parameter for deep-sea oil and gas pipelines. PVDF is resistant to corrosion under severe environmental stresses and it costs much less (USD \$8.8 /kg for PA12 [7] and USD \$14 /kg for PVDF [8] compared to USD \$110 /kg for PEEK 150) and yet it can be processed from approximately 180 °C [9-12]. Nonetheless, when considering the development of carbon fibre reinforced PVDF, and indeed the same is true for other fluoropolymers, the low adhesion at the fibre-matrix interface due to the lack of compatibility between the polymer and carbon fibres is problematic because when a load is applied to a fibre reinforced composite, it is transferred from the matrix to the carbon fibre [13,14]. If the fibre to matrix interaction is weak, it will result in poor mechanical composite performance. This poor adhesion is due to the inert nature of the matrix and the lack of reactive groups as compared to thermosetting systems. In this study, an atmospheric plasma fluorination (APF) process was adapted into a homemade unidirectional fibre reinforced PVDF composites manufacturing line to produce carbon fibre reinforced PVDF composites. Fabricated composite tapes were compression moulded into flexural and short-beam shear test specimens for studying the relationship between surface fluorine content of the carbon fibres and composite interface dominated properties at a macro-mechanical level.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

Two types of polyacrylonitrile (PAN) based commercially available carbon fibres (Torayca T700GC-91 and HexTow™ AS4 12K) were used in this study. Both fibres were high tensile strength, unsized but standard industrially oxidised. The poly vinylidene fluoride (PVDF) used was Kynar® 711 (Arkema, France). The surfactant used to stabilise the suspension of PVDF powder in water was Cremophor® A25 (BASF, Germany). Gases used as feed gas during the plasma modification were chlorodifluoromethane (Freon 22) and nitrogen (N₂) (BOC, UK).

Inline modification and manufacturing

Unidirectional (UD) unsized carbon fibre reinforced PVDF tape of 12.5 mm width and 0.1 mm thick was manufactured using a home built modular laboratory scale composite production line (CPL) (Fig. 1) based on the powder impregnation technique used for thermoplastic composite manufacturing [15-17]. The 12K carbon fibre roving was taken off from a tension controlled let-off unit (Izumi International, USA) and looped 3 times inside a borosilicate glass tee piece over phenolic resin roller pins while exposed to the atmospheric plasma jet (FLUME Jet RD1004, Plasmatreat, Germany). A detailed description of the setup and operational parameters of continuous APF of carbon fibres can be found in Ref. [18]. The fibres were then passed over a series of pins to promote spreading of the fibres in the powder impregnation bath. The impregnation bath contained 9 wt% PVDF and 2 wt% of surfactant with respect to the polymer in 2.5 L of deionised water. The polymer-impregnated fibre tow was then

passed through an infra-red heated drying oven operated at 100°C in order to drive off the water before entering an infra-red heated melting oven operating at 220°C in order to melt the polymer, which causes the impregnation of the fibres. The polymer melt impregnated fibre tow was then passed over a set of three heated pins (220°C) to further spread the molten polymer along the fibre tow before being consolidated by water cooled rollers and into a continuous unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced composite tape. Finally the tape was wound up. Three different manufacturing speeds (0.33 m/min, 0.75 m/min and 1.0 m/min) were chosen, which corresponds to various the residence time (1.8 min, 0.8 min and 0.6 min) of the carbon fibres within the glass chamber of the plasma jet. The processing speed was controlled using a belt-drive pulling unit (Model 110-3, RDN manufacturing Co., USA).

Figure 1: Schematic of unidirectional fibre reinforced polymer production line

Control of fibre volume content of carbon fibre/ PVDF composite tape

The fibre volume content of the manufactured composite tape changes as a function of processing time because the PVDF powder from the impregnation bath is consumed during the manufacturing process. This causes the fibre volume content of the produced composite tape to increase. Therefore, for a consistent carbon fibre/ PVDF composite with a fibre volume fraction of 60 % to be produced, the concentration of PVDF powder in the impregnation bath must be maintained as constant as possible. This was done by adding 50 ml batches of concentrated polymer suspension containing 30 wt-% of PVDF to the impregnation bath approximately every 10, 15 or 20 min depending on the manufacturing speed. These time intervals were established by monitoring the fibre volume (Eq. 2) of the produced carbon fibre/ PVDF composite tape every 10 min.

Unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced PVDF tape samples were collected, cut into 1 m long specimens (Fig. 2) and weighed out using an analytical balance (HR-120-EC, A&D Instruments, UK). The fibre volume content FVC of the carbon fibre/ PVDF tapes were calculated using the following equation:

$$FVC = \frac{\rho_m W_f}{\rho_f W_m + \rho_m W_f} \quad (1)$$

where ρ and W are the density and the weight and f and m correspond to the fibre and the matrix, respectively. (W_f of 1m carbon fibres = 0.858 g, $\rho_f = 1.80 \text{ gcm}^{-3}$, $\rho_m = 1.80 \text{ gcm}^{-3}$). Collected carbon fibre reinforced PVDF tapes were then sorted into FVC range of < 48.5 %, 50 %, 55 %, 60 %, 65 % and > 67.5 %. Only tapes with a FVC of 60 % were used to prepare composite test specimens (Fig. 2).

Figure 2: A photographic image of 1m long carbon fibre reinforced PVDF tape specimens

Preparation of composite test specimen

Unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced PVDF composite laminates test specimens were prepared by cutting the produced composite tape into 15 cm long strands, washed with ethanol to remove oil contamination from human skin and allowed to dry. For each test specimen, 34 layers of the cut composite tapes were stacked and tightly wrapped together using a release film (Upilex 25S, UBE Industries Ltd., Japan) before placing them into a steel mould. Compression moulding of the stacked carbon fibre tapes was carried out by pre-heating the stacked composite tapes for 10 min in a hot press (P319, Moore, UK) at 190 °C before slowly increasing the pressure to 1 t and held for 2 min. The mould was then transferred to another hot press operated at 80 °C and where it was held for 10 min at a pressure of 0.5 t before allowed to cool to ambient temperature. Specimens were then removed and cut to the required dimensions for mechanical testing using a diamond blade cutter (Diadisc 4200, Mutronic GmbH & Co, Germany).

Transverse sections of moulded specimens were embedded into a polyester resin. The resin was cured at room temperature with the addition of an initiator for 24 h before being polished using abrasion discs following the guidelines for soft material (Buehler Ltd, Illinois, USA). Samples were carefully polished due to the fact that carbon dust can easily scratch the resin surface and fill possible voids in the material. Processed specimens were then examined under an optical microscope.

Macromechanical characterisation of carbon fibre/ PVDF composites

The flexural properties and the short beam shear strength were determined by loading the test specimens into a three-point bending rig equipped with a 10 kN load cell (Model 4502, Instron, UK) following the ASTM D790-03 standard [19] and the ASTM standard D2344 [20], respectively. Each specimen was tested until failure and the macromechanical properties were determined from at least 8 measurements in order to obtain a statistically significant average. The values presented are averaged values and errors are standard deviations.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We examine the effect on the mechanical properties by incorporating a continuous APF of carbon fibres into the manufacturing process to produce unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced PVDF composites. X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was used to determine the surface fluorine content of APF treated

carbon fibres (Table 1). A detailed discussion of the characterisation methods can be found in Ref. [21].

Table 1: Surface composition (in at.%) of APF AS4 and T700 carbon fibres determined by XPS

Processing speed/ mmin^{-1}	AS4 F /at.%	T700 F /at.%
0.33	3.7	3.7
0.75	3.0	1.8
1	2.8	1.7

Fig. 3 shows an optical micrograph of typical transverse sections of the manufactured PVDF composite laminates containing unidirectionally aligned APF carbon fibres. The fibre distribution within the composite was generally uniform, although the form of the original individual composite tapes moulded to form the laminates remains clearly evident, as shown by the presence of resin rich regions between the layers of composite tapes.

Figure 3: Representative optical microscopic image of as produced laminated unidirectional carbon fibre reinforced PVDF composites after consolidation and compression moulding

Impact of APF on flexural properties of carbon fibre reinforced PVDF

Flexural properties are important in engineering practice and are used a lot a) to obtain design data, b) for quality control and c) for specification purposes. If the bonding between the fibre and the matrix is weak, which is the case for carbon fibres and fluoropolymers, composites will not support load in shear or compression. The flexural test measures exactly that. A flexural strength of 260 ± 18 MPa was obtained for standard industrially oxidised but unsized T700/ PVDF composites produced at a line speed of 1 m/min (Fig. 2, left). For the composites containing T700 carbon fibres that were continuously APF treated with a degree of fluorination of 1.8 at.-% (produced at 0.75 m/ min), the flexural strength increased to 339 ± 9 MPa, which corresponded to a 30 % increase. As the fluorine content of the carbon fibres increased to 3.7 at.-% (produced at 0.33 m/ min), the flexural strength of the composites was found to increase further by 45 % to 378 ± 16 MPa. A similar trend was also observed to the flexural strength of AS4/ PVDF composites. For the AS4/ PVDF composites containing untreated carbon fibres, the flexural strength was 223 ± 9 MPa. For the composites containing AS4 carbon fibres that were continuously APF with a degree of fluorination of 3 at.-% (produced at 0.75 m/ min), the flexural strength increased to 357 ± 22 MPa,

which corresponded to a 60 % increase. As the fluorine content of the carbon fibres increased to 3.7 at.-% (produced at 0.33 m/ min), the flexural strength of the composites was found to increase further by 108 % to 463 ± 10 MPa.

Figure 2: Flexural strength (left) and modulus (right) of laminated AS4/T700 carbon fibre reinforced PVDF composites as function of fibre surface fluorine content

The flexural modulus increased from 63 ± 5.5 GPa for the standard oxidized but unsized T700/PVDF composites to 79 ± 2.7 GPa for composites that contained carbon fibres that were continuously APF with a degree of fluorination of 1.8 at.-%. As the surface fluorine content of the reinforcing fibre increased further to 3.7 at.-%, the flexural modulus increased to 87 ± 2.5 GPa. A similar trend was also observed to the flexural modulus of AS4/ PVDF composites. For the AS4/ PVDF composites containing untreated carbon fibres, the flexural strength was 79 ± 2.1 GPa. For the composites containing AS4 carbon fibres that were continuously APF with a degree of fluorination of 3 at.-% (produced at 0.75 m/ min), the flexural strength increased to 104 ± 2.8 GPa. As the fluorine content of the carbon fibres increased to 3.7 at.-% (produced at 0.33 m/ min), the flexural modulus of the composites was found to increase further to 110 ± 1.7 GPa.

From the flexural results obtained, we can see that by increasing the fluorine content of both AS4 and T700 fibres, there is a positive impact on the flexural properties of the reinforced PVDF composite laminates. Since the flexural test is an interface dominated property test, by examining the stress acted upon the surface of the specimen at failure, which is accompanied by the breaking of fibres, the results suggest enhancement in interfacial strength between carbon fibres and PVDF.

Impact of APF on apparent short beam shear strength of carbon fibre reinforced PVDF

The apparent short beam shear strength SBS increases from 7.8 MPa for the standard oxidized but unsized T700/PVDF composites to 8.7 MPa and to 10.8 MPa for composites containing carbon fibres with a degree of fluorination of 1.7 at.-% and 1.8 at.-% (Fig. 3). As the surface fluorine content of the reinforcing carbon fibre continues to increase to 3.7 at.-%, the apparent SBS was found to increase further to 13.4 ± 0.4 MPa. The results obtained indicate that appropriate degree of inline carbon fibre modification improves the interface dominated mechanical properties of unidirectional T700 carbon fibre reinforced PVDF. A similar trend was also observed to the apparent SBS of AS4/ PVDF composites. For the AS4/ PVDF composites containing untreated

carbon fibres, the SBS was 7.2 ± 0.2 MPa. For the composites containing AS4 carbon fibres that were continuously APF with a degree of fluorination of 3 at.-% (produced at 0.75 m/ min), the SBS increased to 11.2 ± 0.2 MPa. As the fluorine content of the carbon fibres increased to 3.7 at.-% (produced at 0.33 m/ min), the SBS of the composites was found to increase further to 20.6 ± 0.2 MPa.

Figure 3: Apparent short beam shear strength of laminated AS4/ T700 carbon fibre reinforced PVDF composites as function of fibre surface fluorine content

By applying the SBS test to examine the interlaminar shear strength of carbon fibre reinforced PVDF composites, we are able to investigate the fibre matrix adhesion. Once again we can see from the apparent SBS results obtained that by increasing the fluorine content of both AS4 and T700 fibres, there is a positive impact on the interlaminar shear strength of the reinforced PVDF composite laminates, i.e. improvement in interfacial adhesion. From the data obtained, we can see that the apparent SBS strength values are less than $\sim 9\%$ of the flexural strength recorded. This indicates that the specimens did fail in shear mode rather than in tension.

CONCLUSIONS

The potential of continuous inline atmospheric plasma fluorination of carbon fibres to tailor the fibre/matrix interface while manufacturing unidirectional fibre reinforced PVDF composite tapes was investigated. Thin carbon fibre/ PVDF tapes with a fibre volume fraction of 60 % were produced using a powder impregnation method. By controlling the processing speed, the residence time in the APF plasma jet and thus the degree of fluorination of carbon fibres can be controlled. Carbon fibre/ PVDF tapes were processed into composite laminate test pieces by compression moulding and interface dominated properties of the APF carbon fibre/ PVDF composite laminates were studied. The short-beam shear test showed improvements of up to 72 and 200 % in apparent short beam shear strength for the composite laminates containing APF T700 and AS4 carbon fibres, respectively. Both of these carbon fibres have a fluorine content of 3.7 at.-%, as determined by XPS. Results from flexural tests show that the flexural strength of laminated carbon fibre/ PVDF composites containing APF T700 and AS4 carbon fibres increased by 45 % and 100 %, respectively. The flexural modulus of the laminated carbon fibre/ PVDF composites containing APF T700 and AS4 carbon fibres also increased by 38 % and 40 %, respectively. Initial results from interface dominated properties indicate that good fibre-matrix adhesion was achieved by appropriate degree of inline carbon fibre modification during composite manufacturing.

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